

A DSGE Model to Assess the Impacts of Worker Health on the UK Economy

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Abstract

The UK has suffered from a productivity puzzle since the financial crisis. Micro-level analysis has previously shown that worker health adversely affects individual economic outcomes. However, applying this empirical fact to explain macroeconomic performance is undeveloped. Therefore, this dissertation endogenizes health-sensitive and insensitive workers in a DSGE framework and simulates health shocks that represent absenteeism and presenteeism, which measure productivity loss due to poor worker health. Results from the model find that both shocks damage output and employment and are inflationary. However, presenteeism is considerably more so due to its persistence and imposes a negative externality on workers not directly exposed to the shock, consistent with existing literature and data. Thus, worker health can help explain stagnation in total factor productivity in the UK and internationally. This dissertation further advocates for more health data coverage and policies that increase restitution, discourage exhaustion and reduce the share of the health-sensitive workforce.

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1 Introduction

Literature has explored how worker health impacts individual labour market and economic outcomes, but its ability to explain macroeconomic performance is overlooked. In the UK, the focus region for this dissertation, health outcomes have underperformed other developed countries following the financial crisis on average (Papanicolas et al., 2019). In 2023, 7.5 million patients were waiting for NHS treatments in England, while median wait times have doubled since 2009 (NHS England, 2024a). This outcome results from sustained fiscal pressure and demographic changes that have increased healthcare demand. Sickness absence rates stagnated from their downward trend pre-financial crisis and then jumped to 2.6% in 2022 (Office for National Statistics (ONS), 2023a). The share of employed workers suffering from long-term sickness has also increased by around 8ppts in the last decade to 31%. As a result, poor worker health has weighed on labour market outcomes and productivity; Vitality (2024) estimates of output losses at work are £138 billion (6% of UK GDP), with chronic diseases, mental health and lifestyle choices as influential factors (Bryan, Bryce and Roberts, 2022). Productivity shocks caused by poor worker health observed in the UK have not yet been modelled in a dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) framework.

The UK has also experienced a productivity puzzle, the phenomenon of weak productivity growth since the financial crisis for no idiosyncratic reason; UK productivity is currently 16% below its pre-financial crisis trend (ONS, 2023b). In addition, Van Reenen and Yang (2023) found an incessant productivity shortfall in the UK relative to other advanced economies. Goodridge and Haskel (2023) state that total factor productivity (TFP), a residual term encompassing worker health, has contributed to 78% of the slowdown. Hence, increased persistence and sensitivity to health shocks may be a cause of macroeconomic productivity loss. First, such shocks can trigger work absences; absenteeism is a worker's status when habitually absent. Second, as forgoing work or leaving a job is usually a last resort (Bound et al., 1999), individuals who attend work while ill experience presenteeism (Johns, 2010).

Therefore, this dissertation's research questions aim to assess the impact of poor health outcomes on macroeconomic variables using a New Keynesian (NK) DSGE model. The dissertation will also analyse why health is not commonly cited to explain the UK's productivity puzzle and whether the model results can explain empirical evidence. Finally, this study aims to evaluate UK health policies and recommend new measures to improve health outcomes. If health can explain part of the puzzle, governments and the private sector

must implement cost-effective and efficient health policies to reduce the prolongation of poor health outcomes that would otherwise weigh on UK dynamism. CEP (2023) uncovered that TFP growth is a laggard in other developed countries, so findings from this dissertation may aid future studies in assessing the effect of health shocks on the global economy.

An NK DSGE model with two types of workers, those sensitive and insensitive to health shocks, is adapted from a model by Matsui and Yoshimi (2015). The model presents three shocks: a baseline positive aggregate productivity shock in the production function. Another simulates a negative work absence shock through the health-sensitive workforce's household's labour supply decision (i.e., supply fewer labour hours). Finally, a negative shock representing presenteeism works through the health-sensitive workforce's productivity parameter (i.e., are less productive at work). These shocks incorporate the coexistence and trade-off between absenteeism and presenteeism (Markussen, 2007; Zhang, Bansback and Anis, 2011) and align with the implications of the health economics literature. The simultaneous impacts of the positive productivity shocks and adverse health shocks are compared. The results show that both health shocks have material impacts on output, employment and inflation and offset the effects of positive productivity shocks. However, the impact on output of a presenteeism shock is five times larger than that of an absenteeism shock. Furthermore, presenteeism shocks have damaging implications for those insensitive to health shocks, meaning that policies must aim to reduce the persistence and frequency of longer-term health shocks by utilising technology to improve the health of workforces.

The literature review in section 2 discusses existing studies that detail how health impacts worker outcomes and workplace productivity loss due to presenteeism and absenteeism, which rely primarily on micro-analyses. Additionally, it considers the theoretical literature that models health decisions, shocks, and their effects on worker outcomes and evaluates simple DSGE models with heterogeneous agents. Section 3 presents the DSGE model by solving the household and firm optimisation problems and establishing equilibrium conditions. Section 4 outlines log-linearisation, the data and steady state parameters used for model calibration. Section 5 discusses the shocks' impulse response functions (IRFs) and debates the success of the UK Government and private sector policy. Finally, section 6 concludes and provides policy recommendations to reduce the effects of poor worker health in the UK and internationally.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Empirical Literature Review

A deterioration in workers' health negatively impacts their labour market outcomes. In the UK, studies initially investigated how health impacts retirement decisions. Tanner (1998) found that 72% of British men stated that ill health was a cause of retirement in 1988, and it was the most cited reason among both sexes by the 1990s (Disney, Grundy and Johnson, 1997). More recently, Disney, Emmerson and Wakefield (2006) showed that a unitary increase in an individual's health stock (Bound et al., 1999) decreases the probability of retirement by 45%. Additionally, Jones, Rice and Zantomio (2020) estimated that the average treatment effect (ATT) of an acute health shock increased the risk of exiting the labour market by 40% and caused a 3ppt reduction in hours worked along the intensive margin for those that continued to work using data between 2009-2016. The latter result conflicts with a pre-financial-crisis study by Lenhart (2019) that showed little effect on the intensive margin. These studies use different data sets (British Household Panel Survey vs UK Household Longitudinal Survey (UKHLS), which may have caused selection bias) and econometric designs (coarsened exact matching method versus differences-in-differences); however, if these results are comparable, it may exemplify a change in behaviour in response to a health shock between these two periods. This change could be due to the rise in mental health, which increases the probability of non-employment than most physical diseases (García-Gómez, Jones, and Rice, 2010), but the effects vary between sexes (Contoyannis and Rice, 2001). These results emphasise the importance of health on labour market outcomes.

International literature arrives at similar results (Arrow, 1996; García-Gómez and Nicolás, 2006; Smith, 2004). Pertinently, García-Gómez (2011) performs a European comparison to show that health shocks reduce the probability of employment, but her results suggest the ATT is inconclusive, ranging from a 6.9% decrease in Denmark to a 2.0% increase in France, partly explained by different social security arrangements. On the contrary, Riphahn (1999) found that health shocks increase the probability of unemployment by 84% in German workers aged 40-59; the severity of this change is due to the stringency of the health shock's definition and the age group's vulnerability. Furthermore, Stewart (2001) found that impaired health leads to longer-duration unemployment spells in Canada; the UKHLS has not yet been utilised to replicate this study in the UK. Results of global literature transfer to the UK

somewhat but could vary depending on the health shock type and treatment, different policy environments and demographics, and necessary controls would be required.

Secondly, poor health causes adverse consequences on income and productivity. Lenhart's (2019) difference-in-differences analysis isolated the ATTs of health shocks over three to nine years. In the nine-year sample, nearest neighbour matching estimators find a reduction of labour income by £4,400 (~20%). He also indicates that marginal labour productivity deteriorates after a health shock, showing that health shocks can influence structural economic growth outcomes. Madden (2004) observes wage discrimination between UK males who are able and disabled, finding that health status' effect on productivity directly accounts for approximately a third of wage variation, lower than Kidd, Sloane and Ferko (1998) who estimated 50% but did not control for health or employment selection. Furthermore, Lenhart (2019) showed that health shocks increased the likelihood of a worker reporting health-related work problems by 20% and had persistence over long sample periods. Fischer, Reade and Schmal (2022) claim COVID-19 has compromised performance of elite athletes by 5% eight months after infection, highlighting that health shocks can have lasting effects (i.e., presenteeism). These outcomes are also reflected in international studies (Lindelow and Wagstaff, 2005; García-Gómez and Nicolás, 2006; Aleksandrova, Bagranova and Gerry, 2021; Wang, Jin and Yuan, 2023). Overall, small-sample evidence reveals a strong correlation between health and productivity, necessitating a model to assess the macroeconomic effects and the implications on those not directly exposed to health shocks.

Endogeneity is a limitation of empirical surveys that assess the relationship between individual economic outcomes and health. First, mismeasurement problems can arise through self-reported health status from justification bias. Second, endogeneity could emerge through simultaneity bias. In early post-war British studies, Brenner (1983) showed the predictability of morbidity and mortality rates using per capita real incomes, unemployment rates, and shorter-term cyclicalities in mortality rates. A recession will moderate investments in healthcare services and consequently reduce the probability of reemployment when the downturn ends (Jones, 1991), leading to adverse feedback effects. However, isolating the initial impact of unexpected and random health shocks can help circumvent these sources of endogeneity. Furthermore, instrumental variables or regression discontinuity designs address omitted variable bias. Thus, the collective results of the literature warrant further investigation of the macroeconomic consequences of health shocks.

Since the financial crisis, a paradigm of lacklustre UK labour productivity growth has emerged; annual productivity growth slowed to 0.5% between 2008-19 (Figure 1) versus 1.9% between 1990-2007 (ONS, 2023b). European countries, the US and Canada have experienced a comparable slowdown (ONS, 2023c), but the UK has witnessed the most divergence from its pre-crisis trend amongst the G7. Productivity trend growth rates drive underlying real wage growth and living standards. The bifurcation in the UK productivity debate is to explain why absolute *and* relative productivity growth compared to peers is so weak. Considering the former, common explanations of the productivity puzzle include the mismeasurement of intangible assets or overestimation of financial sector productivity pre-financial crisis given the sector's size (Goodridge, Haskel and Wallis, 2014; Chadha, Kara and Labonne, 2017). The subsequent crisis caused lower capital deepening which has been exacerbated by financial frictions (Goodridge and Haskel, 2016; Chadha, Kara and Labonne, 2017, Van Reenen and Yang, 2023). However, others suggest occupational mismatches and lack of skills are the cause (Smith, 2012; Patterson et al., 2016; Van Reenen and Yang, 2023), but the latter is disputed with big data analysis of job vacancies (Turrell et al., 2021). Finally, Coyle and Mei (2023) state that a labour force composition change has led to a reallocation to unproductive sectors (e.g., finance, manufacturing, and ICT), explaining part of the puzzle but disregarding large sectoral and regional productivity dispersions (ONS, 2022).

Figure 1: UK GDP, employment, labour productivity is well below trend. Source: ONS (2023b). Note that labour productivity is GVA divided by the number of labour hours worked.

However, to answer the research question, international comparisons prove more insightful; disaggregation analysis shows TFP has contributed 78% of the decline in productivity growth, a pattern reflected across the G7 (Goodridge and Haskel, 2023; Fernald and Inklaar, 2022; Van Reenen and Yang, 2023). TFP growth usually originates from technological progress but encompasses health because it is a residual term (Cole and Neumayer, 2006). For example, Bloom et al. (2020) showed that TFP declined between 3-5% after the onset of COVID-19 and that firm-level productivity correlated with its sensitivity to the shock, suggesting the UK is sensitive to health shocks. Although a short-term shock like COVID-19 may not have affected trend growth (Fernald and Li, 2022), a series of small, persistent health shocks over a business cycle is likely to affect long-term productivity growth; this premise can be constructed a DSGE model by endogenizing health-sensitive and insensitive workers.

Health is an overlooked factor of the productivity puzzle, despite unanimity regarding the influence of health status on individual productivity. Attention has been paid to the output loss of those leaving the labour force due to sickness, though this does not necessarily explain the decline in productivity. Parsonage (2007) asserts that turnover costs of workers quitting their jobs are a small fraction of the costs of lost productivity at work, so excluding search frictions and job matching is a simplifying assumption applied to the model. However, Figure 2 shows that there has been a significant rise in the percentage of individuals who have long-term sickness within the economically active over the last decade (ONS, 2023d), which highlights the threat of absenteeism and presenteeism on economic outcomes.

In addition, there is no nationally defined measure for health or methodology to quantify health-related costs (Parsonage, 2007; Hemp, 2004). Lofland, Pizzi and Frick (2004) describe the human-capital approach that determines the productivity loss from lost earnings from a disease or disorder by surveys. For example, Koopman et al. (2002) developed the Stanford Presenteeism Scale (SPS-6) that asks six different questions of workers to assess the prevalence of presenteeism. Regardless, health is intrinsically challenging to monitor, and data is often unavailable due to its sensitivity, even if anonymised. The stigma around poor health or misdiagnoses could have caused misreporting (Isham, Mair and Jackson et al., 2020). Some progress has been made in overcoming these constraints and improving UK worker health and transparency. For example, in 2016, the UK Government commissioned the Taylor Review (Taylor et al., 2017), which suggested that firms should develop physical

and mental health support for workers to improve and measure worker quality and productivity. However, most recommendations from this report are yet to be implemented.

Figure 2: Share of UK workers in employment aged 16-64 that are suffering from health conditions or illnesses lasting more than one year, the time series is a 12-month rolling average. Source: ONS (2023d).

The lack of arguments about health is also surprising due to profound health inequalities in the UK. Before the crisis, health inequalities were already more pronounced in the UK relative to all European countries except Denmark, conditioning on income inequality (van Doorslaer and Koolman, 2004). The financial crisis and subsequent austerity may have since caused further worsening. For example, health departmental spending grew only 1.5% in real terms on average between 2010-19, in contrast to 3.7% before this period since the 1950s (The King's Fund, 2019). Moreover, health capital investment was only half the OECD average as a percentage of GDP during the 2010s (The Health Foundation, 2019). Literature investigating the impact of lower local-level authority spending cuts has suggested negative implications for health, particularly for mental health in poorer areas (Barr, Kindeman and Whitehead, 2015; Niedzweidz et al., 2016; Bhandari, 2019). Health disparities and mortality rates have also diverged between the North and South of England (Buchan et al., 2017); Brown et al. (2019) find that health inequalities explain a third of the differences in regional UK productivity, although it is not necessarily causal. This analysis aligns with a US finding that concludes health shocks account for 15% of lifetime income inequalities (Smith, 2004).

Calculations have been made to estimate the macroeconomic cost of poor health by measuring absenteeism and presenteeism. Absenteeism causes a loss of productivity through tacit knowledge, interconnectedness between employees and when there is a lack of worker substitution (Grinza and Rycx, 2020). The study finds that a 1ppt rise in the rate of absenteeism causes a productivity loss of 0.24% using Belgian data. In the UK, absenteeism costs are more accessible to measure than presenteeism as national data is available from the ONS. In 2009, Black and Frost (2011) found that employers paid £9 billion in sick pay benefits, roughly aligning with earlier estimates using the ONS, CBI, and CPID data from 2006 (Parsonage, 2007). Parsonage and Saini (2017) stated that costs rose 29% to £10.8 billion in 2016-17 under the same methodology. Population growth likely caused this difference because the sickness absence rate declined during this period (ONS, 2023a). In 2011, the Centre for Mental Health found that mental health-related absenteeism costs were £8.4 billion. Vitality's Healthiest Workplace Survey utilises regressions alongside a survey-based approach to model how job- and workplace-related, personal, health and physical factors affect productivity annually (Hafner et al., 2015). In the year to October 2023, Vitality (2024) sampled 4,787 employees at 59 organisations; the data implied absenteeism costs were £17 billion. The last decade's rise is likely due to increased part-time workers, working from home, the ageing population, health service quality and repercussions from COVID-19.

Presenteeism's prevalence and associated costs are greater than absenteeism (Ramsey, 2006; Garrow, 2015), but estimates are derived through less reliable methodologies. Bryan, Bryce and Roberts (2022) construct probit models utilising the Short Form 12 Health Survey from the UKHLS. They find the onset of a physical or mental health disease increases the probability of the onset of dysfunctional presenteeism by 7ppts and 12ppts, respectively, and 9% of the population suffers from dysfunctional presenteeism each month; the authors do not measure aggregate presenteeism costs. The latter result is significantly less than Robertson et al. (2012) that surveyed 6,309 employees across seven different health, education and governmental organisations in the UK between 2009-10 and found that 60% suffered from presenteeism in the three months prior and presenteeism rates increased with tenure – but such a small sample size lacks external validity. Note that presenteeism can also be functional, supporting workers' mental and physical health in a positive working environment. Another technique by Parsonage and Saini (2017) found presenteeism associated with mental health illnesses was £21.2 billion, up 40% from 2006 (Parsonage, 2007). However, the latter uses international literature to formulate a cost estimate, which

raises reliability concerns. Another estimate from the Centre for Mental Health (2011) proposed that presenteeism costs were around £15 billion due to mental health. More recently, Vitality (2024) implied the cost of presenteeism to be approximately £120 billion, seven times greater than absenteeism, consistent with a similar US study (Dixon, 2005). The exponential increase in presenteeism costs may partially reflect the reductions in sampling size in the Vitality survey or changes in reporting behaviour after the pandemic. Nevertheless, the literature shows that health, particularly mental health, is a driver of productivity loss.

2.2 Theoretical Literature Review

Grossman's (1972 and 2000) adaptations of Becker's (1962) human capital model presented health as a durable consumption and investment good and the theoretical foundations for optimal health decisions. Health capital dictates time spent in market-based activities thus underpins the stock of knowledge; individuals increase their health stock through investments in health-related goods. There are debates about the model's empirical usefulness, whereby it cannot explain the negative correlation between health capital and medical care found empirically (Zweifel, 2012; Kaestner, 2013). However, Grossman's (1972) assumptions and the broader health literature show that sick time is unproductive and individuals can change their susceptibility to health shocks through their lifestyle decisions in the long run.

Grossman's (1972) model helps observe the responsiveness of health to decision-making but fails to account for the stochasticity of health; McGuire, Henderson and Mooney (1988) correct this by basing health capital depreciation on a probability distribution, although this augmentation decreases analytical tractability. Moreover, Grossman's framework has limited applicability to absenteeism and presenteeism—a more relevant stream of literature models random health shocks. Health shocks refer to an unexpected decline in an individual's health caused by illness or injury, have varying degrees of persistence and severity and are modelled as autoregressive processes (Bound et al., 1999; Abo-Zaid and Sheng, 2020). These models utilise empirical studies to evaluate labour market and productivity outcomes as mentioned in section 2.1 and will inform absenteeism and presenteeism shock setups in the DSGE model.

Chatterji and Tilley (2002) review the supply-side, efficiency wage and contract approaches to explain absenteeism; namely, a worker's optimal choice problem is constrained due to the expectation of them by a firm to honour a labour contract to work for a specific number of hours. However, as Bound et al. (1999) eloquently phrase, 'ceasing to perform an activity is only one response and often the response of last resort'. Health shocks can occur at any time

in an individual's life, and presenteeism may instead act as the first line of defence. Chatterji and Tilley (2002) incorporate presenteeism by introducing a health index, whereby the utility and the marginal utility of consumption decrease in ill health; this approach leads to a discrete choice model, which in equilibrium states that presenteeism and absenteeism cannot co-exist. However, absenteeism and presenteeism are not independent concepts which complicate their measurement; instead, an individual is presented with a trade-off when deciding to work whilst ill (Markussen, 2007; Zhang, Bansback and Anis, 2011). If an ill worker chooses absence, productivity will improve faster (restitution) than attending work (exhaustion). Equally, a healthy worker choosing to work will benefit from this decision (reward for working) over abstaining. Markussen (2007) also hypothesizes there may be two levels of health between which an individual is indifferent between working and abstaining. Furthermore, Hirsch, Lechmann and Schnabel (2015) use continuous parameters denoting the share of time at work and a health scale parameter to illustrate a dynamic trade-off and state presenteeism and absenteeism occurring in equilibrium. This trade-off implies that absenteeism and presenteeism shocks occur simultaneously on an aggregate level.

From a macroeconomic perspective, labour productivity is a function of TFP, the quality of labour (labour composition) and capital per quality-adjusted unit of labour (capital deepening) as shown in equation (2.1). Y_t is output, H_t is the number of hours worked, TFP_t is TFP, LC_t is labour composition, K_t is capital input and α_t represents the capital share of income; taking logarithmic changes shows the growth of these parameters over time. Absenteeism is represented by a decrease in hours worked and output, each of which has counteracting effects on labour productivity. Presenteeism does not affect hours worked but reduces output so therefore must be encapsulated in the TFP parameter. Crucially, both only affect a fraction of the workforce, so endogenizing workers into those vulnerable to health shocks will help explain how labour productivity is affected by health more effectively.

$$\Delta \ln Y_t - \Delta \ln H_t = \Delta \ln TFP_t + (1 - \alpha_t) \Delta \ln LC_t + \alpha_t (\Delta \ln K_t - \Delta \ln H_t) \quad (2.1)$$

DSGE models are quantitative simulations that attempt to explain short-run business cycle fluctuations. A system of endogenous aggregate macroeconomic variables and exogenous shock variables formulates a system of log-linearised equations; changes in the exogenous variables cause economic agents to continuously recalibrate their optimal economic

behaviour during these periods. To answer the research questions, a regular NK DSGE model is adapted to illustrate health shocks that characterise absenteeism and presenteeism.

Several functional forms could convey these concepts, such as those with two types of labour, previously used to illustrate labour supply decisions of union or gig economy workers (Matsui and Yoshimi, 2015; Okolo, 2021). Alternatively, an effort variable could be integrated to reflect productivity at work (Bils and Cho, 1994; Kim and Shim, 2020). Another approach by Vasilev (2017) augmented Grossman's framework into a DSGE model that simulates a TFP shock and 1ppt unanticipated innovation in health investment productivity on the economy, although it does not disaggregate effects into absenteeism and presenteeism. Post-COVID-19-pandemic literature also has called for a more critical look at the impact of health shocks. For example, early-stage evidence suggests the pandemic positively changed behaviours towards exercise (Powell, 2022). In addition, Abo-Zaid and Sheng (2020) integrated health shocks in a two-sector DSGE model whereby only one sector is affected by the state of public health; this may not accurately reflect health shocks that affect all workers regardless of sector. Martin and Okolo (2022) characterised monetary and fiscal policy responses from the pandemic to observe the subsequent employment prospects of graduates versus non-graduates; this model contrasts with the aim of this dissertation to explain how and why health shocks trigger these responses from fiscal and monetary authorities. Finally, Keogh-Brown et al. (2020) use a computable general equilibrium model to find that the pandemic had a direct cost of £38.9 billion attributed to labour supply, £30.8 billion of these economic losses are due to work absence; although this study uses an arbitrary assumption that infections lead to seven days of absence. Section 3 abstracts the features of Matsui and Yoshimi (2015) and Abo-Zaid and Sheng (2020) to answer the research questions, simplifying where necessary to allow future research to build upon this work.

3 Model

3.1 Households

This section discusses an adapted version of the NK DSGE model used by Matsui and Yoshimi (2015) for the research question. A representative household supplies productive labour hours for a wage. Productive labour hours are either worked under S-contracts or N-contracts. In other words, type-S workers (working under S-contracts) are sensitive to health shocks and type-N workers (working under N-contracts) are not sensitive to health shocks. Type-N workers' productivity is independent of any health shocks, but this does not imply that their labour supply decisions are independent of such shocks due to the substitutability between workers. Otherwise, assume all labour units and characteristics are identical.

Equation 3.1 characterises the representative household's constant relative risk aversion (CRRA) utility function like that of Abo-Zaid and Zhang (2020) but is a single-sector model. The utility function illustrates positive diminishing marginal utility of consumption where C_t denotes the composite consumption good and increasing marginal disutility of work from type-S and type-N labour hours, aggregated as $L_{S,t}$ and $L_{N,t}$ respectively. The two types of labour hours are weighted equally. The parameter σ is the Arrow-Pratt measure of relative risk aversion, and the parameter γ is the inverse of the Frisch elasticity of labour supply, which explains the substitution effect with respect to wage rate changes.

$$U(C_t, L_{S,t}, L_{N,t}) = \frac{C_t^{1-\sigma}}{1-\sigma} - \frac{L_{S,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} - \frac{L_{N,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma}, \quad \sigma, \gamma > 0 \quad (3.1)$$

Where $\frac{\delta U}{\delta C_t} > 0$, $\frac{\delta^2 U}{\delta C_t^2} < 0$, $\frac{\delta U}{\delta L_{S,t}} < 0$, $\frac{\delta U}{\delta L_{N,t}} < 0$, $\frac{\delta^2 U}{\delta L_{S,t}^2} < 0$, $\frac{\delta^2 U}{\delta L_{N,t}^2} < 0$.

Aggregate labour inputs are continuously distributed in the unit interval:

$$L_{i,t} = \int_0^1 L_{i,j,t} dj, \quad i = S, N \quad (3.2)$$

where monopolistically competitive firms are denoted by j . The Dixit-Stiglitz aggregator in equation 3.3 shows that the composite consumption good is composed of a continuum of differentiated consumption goods, c_j . The elasticity of substitution between goods, θ , is a measure of substitutability between the goods and the firm's pricing power.

$$C_t = \left[\int_0^1 c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{\theta-1}} \quad (3.3)$$

Households minimise consumption expenditure combinations for a given level of the aggregate consumption good. Equation 3.4 shows that the demand for a differentiated good, c_{jt} , depends on the good's price elasticity of demand ($-\theta$) and its relative price and that households prefer variety due to the diminishing marginal utility of each differentiated good. Appendix 8.1 provides a complete derivation of the household optimisation problem.

$$c_{jt} = \left(\frac{p_{jt}}{P_t} \right)^{-\theta} C_t \quad (3.4)$$

The aggregate price level is given by:

$$P_t = \left[\int_0^1 p_{jt}^{1-\theta} dj \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\theta}} \quad (3.5)$$

Equation 3.6 depicts the household's budget constraint. The right-hand-side shows income sources from wages from S- and N-contracts, $w_{S,t}$ and $w_{N,t}$ respectively, zero-coupon bonds, B_t , which have a price Q_t and yield a gross nominal interest rate Q_t^{-1} between times t and $t + 1$, and firm dividends, Π_t . Type-S labour productivity, $\chi_{1,t}$, reflects the ability of the worker to supply labour, evolves with an AR(1) process and is multiplied by the household's aggregate income from S-contracts. The shock's persistence from the previous period is captured by ρ_1 and $e_{1,t}$ is a white noise variable. The left-hand side shows total expenditure on private consumption and bonds in the current period, at prices P_t and Q_t respectively.

$$P_t C_t + Q_t B_t \leq B_{t-1} + w_{S,t} \chi_{1,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} + \Pi_t \quad (3.6)$$

$$\chi_{1,t} = \rho_1 \chi_{1,t-1} + e_{1,t}, \quad \rho_1 \in (0,1), e_{1,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_{e_1}) \quad (3.7)$$

Given the demand index, the infinitely lived household maximises its expected dynasty welfare, shown by equation 3.8, subject to its budget constraint, with respect to $C_t, B_t, L_{S,t}, L_{N,t}$. β is the discount factor and the budget constraint is binding.

$$\max_{C_t, B_t, L_{S,t}, L_{N,t}} E_t \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \beta^t \left[\frac{C_t^{1-\sigma}}{1-\sigma} - \frac{L_{S,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} - \frac{L_{N,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} \right] \right\} \quad (3.8)$$

The Euler equation 3.9 indicates the marginal utility of consumption in the current period is equal to the expected future marginal utility of consumption weighted by the discount factor, gross nominal interest rate and the inverse of the inflation rate in next period, denoted by π_{t+1} . The net nominal interest rate, r_t , approximates to $r_t \approx -\ln(Q_t)$.

$$C_t^{-\sigma} = \beta(1 + r_t) E_t \left(\frac{C_{t+1}^{-\sigma}}{1 + \pi_{t+1}} \right) \quad (3.9)$$

The inflation rate is defined as:

$$\pi_t = \frac{P_t}{P_{t-1}} - 1 \quad (3.10)$$

Second, the labour-leisure trade-offs are shown for the two different types of labour in equations 3.11 and 3.12. These conditions state the marginal disutility of labour, the product of the cost of supplying a labour hour at the margin and the marginal utility of consumption, is equal to the real wage rate, the benefit of providing a labour hour at the margin. The productivity parameter adjusts the real wage rate of type-S workers.

$$\frac{\chi_{1,t} W_{S,t}}{P_t} = L_{S,t}^{\gamma} C_t^{\sigma} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\frac{W_{N,t}}{P_t} = L_{N,t}^{\gamma} C_t^{\sigma} \quad (3.12)$$

Matsui and Yoshimi (2015) describe a model whereby one type of worker negotiates wages with firms; this dissertation extracts a case from this model whereby the firm has complete bargaining power; thus, wages of type-S and N workers are equal to the Walrasian wage in equilibrium (i.e., under no productivity shocks). This assumption is reasonable as this dissertation only endeavours to show the effect of a portion of the population experiencing asymmetric health shocks with no wage bargaining. Moreover, this leaves scope for future research to reintroduce labour bargaining power into the model and other heterogeneous labour properties (e.g., skill level).

3.2 Firms

Firms possess the production technology to employ both type-S and N workers; capital is abstracted from the model. The production function, equation 3.13, takes a constant elasticity of substitution (CES) form, such that L_t is a population adjusted sum of workers and A_t is an aggregate productivity parameter with an AR(1) process, similar to Kim (2017). The shock's persistence is represented by ρ_A and $e_{A,t}$ is a white noise variable.

$$Y_t = A_t L_t \quad (3.13)$$

$$L_t = \left\{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \right\}^{\frac{1}{\nu}}, \quad \epsilon \in (0,1) \quad (3.14)$$

$$A_t = \rho_A A_{t-1} + e_{A,t}, \quad \rho_A \in (0,1), e_{A,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_{e_A}) \quad (3.15)$$

The firm's elasticity of substitution between workers is $1/(1 - \nu)$. The parameter ϵ is the weight of the health-sensitive worker labour force in the firm's production function. Cantore et al. (2015) describe that ϵ can be represented as a share of the workforce once the equations are normalised and expressed around a steady state value. This makes a simplifying assumption that the share of type-S workers is constant overtime; this is conceivable as productivity shocks only hit a fraction of workers in a single period. Two types of workers are modelled as the empirical evidence shows that only a fraction of the labour force suffers from presenteeism or sickness absence, this is discussed in section 4.1, and it allows exploration of the spillover effects on those not directly affected by health shocks.

Further, assume the productivity of both types of workers is equal to one in steady state, but the productivity of the type-S workers is $\chi_{2,t}$, which also has an AR(1) process. Thus, type-S workers' productivity is subject to an asymmetric health shock that affects their ability to work productively. The persistence of this shock is represented by ρ_2 and $e_{2,t}$ is a white noise variable in equation 3.16.

$$\chi_{2,t} = \rho_2 \chi_{2,t-1} + e_{2,t}, \quad \rho_2 \in (0,1), e_{2,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_{e_2}) \quad (3.16)$$

A representative firm minimises its labour costs subject to the aggregate labour index. This problem derives the firm's demand index for each labour type shown in equation 3.17 and 3.18. Type-S workers' efficiency wage is $w_{S,t}/\chi_{2,t}$. Appendix 8.2 provides a full derivation of the firm's optimisation problem.

$$L_{S,t} = \chi_{2,t}^{\frac{v}{1-v}} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{w_{S,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{v-1}} L_t \quad (3.17)$$

$$L_{N,t} = \left(\frac{1}{1-\epsilon} \frac{w_{N,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{v-1}} L_t \quad (3.18)$$

The aggregate wage index is formulated as:

$$w_t = \left\{ \epsilon^{\frac{1}{1-v}} \left[\frac{w_{S,t}}{\chi_{2,t}} \right]^{\frac{v}{v-1}} + (1-\epsilon)^{\frac{1}{1-v}} [w_{N,t}]^{\frac{v}{v-1}} \right\}^{\frac{v-1}{v}} \quad (3.19)$$

Calvo (1983) suggested a more tractable staggered approach to firms' price setting derived using the Poisson distribution. A fraction of firms, or the probability that firms can change prices in each period, is measured as $(1 - \omega)$; ω indicates the extent to which nominal rigidities exist. Equation 3.20 shows how Calvo pricing affects equation 3.5; P_{t-1} is aggregate price level in the previous period and p_{jt}^* is the optimal price chosen by firms that can change prices in the current period.

$$P_t = [(1 - \omega)p_{jt}^*]^{1-\theta} + \omega P_{t-1}^{1-\theta} \quad (3.20)$$

Firms maximise the discounted value of expected profits subject to the household's demand index in equation 3.4, the production function in equation 3.13 and Calvo's price assumption in equation 3.20. Profits are discounted at rate $\Delta_{t,t+k}$ and $tc_{t+k,t}$ and $mc_{t+k,t}$ is the firm's nominal total and marginal cost of production for a firm in period $t + k$ that last set its price in period t , respectively.

$$\max_{p_{jt}^*} E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} \left[p_{jt}^* \left(\frac{p_{jt}^*}{P_{t+k}} \right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} - tc_{jt+k,t} \left(\left(\frac{p_{jt}^*}{P_{t+k}} \right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (3.21)$$

All firms will choose the same optimal price given that they face the same demand curves, thus $p_{jt}^* = p_t^*$. Moreover, assume the firm and household discount rates are equal, given that households own the firms and receive dividends.

$$\Delta_{t,t+k} = \frac{1}{1+r_t} = \beta^k \left(\frac{C_{t+k}}{C_t} \right)^{-\sigma} E_t \left(\frac{P_t}{P_{t+k}} \right) \quad (3.22)$$

The optimal real price is a weighted average of current and expected real marginal costs:

$$\frac{p_t^*}{P_t} = \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \frac{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} \left(\frac{P_{t+k}}{P_t} \right)^{\theta-1} \left(\frac{mc_{t+k,t}}{P_t} \right) \right\}}{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} \left(\frac{P_{t+k}}{P_t} \right)^{\theta-1} \right\}} \quad (3.23)$$

When there are no nominal price rigidities ($\omega = 0$) all firms charge a frictionless steady-state markup over the marginal cost; see equation 3.24. This also removes the need for a monetary authority and reverts to the standard RBC model with monopolistic competition.

$$p_t^* = \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} mc_t \quad (3.24)$$

Staggered price setting derives the forward-looking NK Phillips Curve (equation 3.26), which states that current inflation depends upon inflation expectations and the log deviation of real marginal cost. Thus, the current inflation rate, π_t , is decreasing in β and ω as firms put less weight on the expected future value of real marginal costs.

$$\pi_t = \beta E_t \pi_{t+1} + \frac{(1-\omega)(1-\beta\omega)}{\omega} (\widehat{mc}_t - \widehat{P}_t) \quad (3.25)$$

3.3 Monetary Policy

A monetary authority sets the net nominal interest rate, r_t , to achieve a target interest rate through a Taylor rule. Equation 3.26 denotes the interest rate gap, where \bar{r}_t is the net nominal interest rate in steady state, is a function of the current inflation rate, π_t , the output gap, Y_t/\bar{Y}_t , and the monetary authority's sensitivities to these variables represented by ϕ_π and ϕ_Y , respectively. $e_{r,t}$ is a white noise policy shock; this could be utilised in future models to evaluate how central banks could respond to the impacts of health shocks.

$$\frac{r_t}{\bar{r}_t} = \pi_t^{\phi_\pi} \left(\frac{Y_t}{\bar{Y}_t} \right)^{\phi_Y} e_{r,t}, \quad e_{r,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_{e_r}) \quad (3.26)$$

3.4 Market Clearing

Imposing market clearing conditions on the model, the total output of the economy is the aggregated output across the continuum of firms. To ensure market equilibrium in the goods market, aggregate demand for goods equals aggregate supply of goods produced.

$$Y_t = \left[\int_0^1 y_{jt}^{\frac{1-\theta}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{1-\theta}} \quad (3.27)$$

$$Y_t = C_t \quad (3.28)$$

Equation 3.30 describes the aggregate demand equation, combining the goods market clearing condition with the household's intertemporal consumption decision (i.e., the Euler equation). Under Walras' Law, the bond market also clears.

$$Y_t^{-\sigma} = \beta(1 + r_t) E_t \left(\frac{Y_{t+1}^{-\sigma}}{1 + \pi_{t+1}} \right) \quad (3.29)$$

Assume that workers have full mobility across firms. Equation 3.30 and 3.31 describe the labour market equilibria (equating labour demand to labour supply).

$$\frac{\chi_{1,t} w_{S,t}}{P_t} = \chi_{2,t}^{\frac{\nu}{1-\nu}} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{w_{S,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} Y_t^\sigma L_t \quad (3.30)$$

$$\frac{w_{N,t}}{P_t} = \left(\frac{1}{1-\epsilon} \frac{w_{N,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} Y_t^\sigma L_t \quad (3.31)$$

Equation 3.32 describes aggregate Calvo prices by substituting in equation 3.23 into 3.20. The aggregate price level is a weighted average of previous and optimal prices, which are a function of expected future marginal costs.

$$P_t = \left[(1 - \omega) \left(\frac{\theta}{\theta - 1} \frac{E_t \{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} P_{t+k}^{\theta-1} m_{C_{t+k,t}} \}}{E_t \{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} P_{t+k}^{\theta-1} \}} \right)^{1-\theta} + \omega P_{t-1}^{1-\theta} \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\theta}} \quad (3.32)$$

4 Estimation

4.1 Data

Estimating the share of the workforce sensitive to health shocks and the duration of ill-health spells is essential. The Annual Population Survey (APS) has a large sample size (~320,000 individuals) and includes the Labour Force Survey and other sample boosts (ONS, 2023d). The APS provides a granular breakdown of economically active individuals with short- and long-term illnesses, albeit a 12-month rolling average. A data discontinuity arose in 2013 when disability-related questions were aligned with other UK household surveys (ONS, 2014). Additionally, the self-reported data introduces potential biases influenced by evolving social attitudes towards health, although it remains anonymised.

The APS addresses absenteeism by asking, 'In [a given week], did you have any days off work because you were sick or injured?' (ONS, 2023e). For context, US employers suggest that an acceptable absence rate for a healthy worker is 1.5% (BrightHR, 2024). In 2022, the UK witnessed a rise in the sickness absence rate to 2.6% after stagnation from its downward trend since 2012 (Figure 3), equivalent to 190 million working days (ONS, 2023a). Notably, the number of days lost per worker reached 5.7, its highest since 2005 and approximately 30% higher than pre-pandemic. This percentage change aligns with empirical studies (CIPD, 2023; NHS England, 2024b; Vitality, 2024), although the absolute values exhibit modest sectoral variations. However, the APS fails to provide a share of those suffering from absenteeism. Meanwhile, UK Government studies in 2009 and 2014 indicated that the proportion of individuals taking any absence ranged between 42-48% (Young and Bhaumik, 2011; Department for Work and Pensions (DWP), 2014). Information on work absence duration is scarce; prior estimates suggest that around 90% of absences last less than one week (Bevan and Hayday, 2001), which implies an absenteeism shock has small persistence.

The rate of presenteeism is extrapolated from the APS, offering estimates of the proportion of sick individuals relative to the employed population (Figure 2). The survey inquires, 'Do you have any physical or mental health conditions or illnesses lasting or expecting to last 12 months or more?' (ONS, 2023e). The latest data reveals that this share for individuals aged 16–64 is 31% (ONS, 2023d). This result is similar to the European Working Conditions Telephone Survey 2021 (Martin, 2023), which found that 34% said they had worked when sick in the last 12 months; both provide slightly lower figures than other surveys. Specifically, 44% of workers reported working on days that should have been designated as

sick leave (DWP, 2014), while Vitality's figures suggested a 45% share in 2019 (Vitality, 2020). The latter statistics are used in calibration because they observe broader lifestyle choices like sleep and diet affect work productivity and known conditions; it is vital to take in this breadth to refine policy decisions. Interestingly, the most recent Vitality (2024) survey implies the loss of 43.6 days due to presenteeism, equating to roughly a sixth of days worked in a year. This suggests a 16.7% decline in productive hours for the average worker, which Vitality attributes a decline of 'only' 5.3% of GDP, this highlights a methodological issue. Nonetheless, to cause such an output decline, the data shows that presenteeism shocks persist significantly, primarily due to chronic illnesses. The DWP (2014) reported that 80% of long-term sick workers returned to their jobs, although the work does not describe the length of the spells experienced. To summarise, around 45% of workers experience both absenteeism and presenteeism, but the persistence of the presenteeism shock is large relative to the absenteeism shock.

Figure 3: UK sickness absence rates between 1995-2022, increasing sharply in 2022. Source: ONS (2023a).

4.2 Calibration

The model contains eight structural and three exogenous shock parameters calibrated to align with existing UK DSGE literature by characterising stylised facts or using data to answer the research question (Table 1). Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011) adopt a similar utility function in a wage bargaining model; the time discount factor, β , the relative risk aversion coefficient, σ , and the inverse of Frisch labour supply elasticity take values 0.99, 0.66 and 1,

respectively, and are also used throughout DSGE literature (Smets and Wouters, 2007; Gertler, Sala and Trigari, 2008; Listios, Pilbeam, and Asteriou, 2020). Calvo's price stickiness parameter, ω , is set to 0.7; there is some disagreement between the model (Faccini, Millard and Zanetti, 2011; DiCecio and Nelson, 2007) and empirical literature. Dixon and Tian (2017) state that firms' average price duration is around eleven months (consistent with $\omega = 0.7$). Meanwhile, the theoretical lower bound is around six months (consistent with $\omega = 0.5$). The empirical result is chosen, but the parameter does not substantially influence the model's results. Moreover, Bunn and Ellis (2012) assert that the probability of price changes is not constant over time. Finally, the Taylor rule sensitivity parameters to inflation, ϕ_π , and the output gap, ϕ_Y , are set to 1.5 and 0.25, respectively; similar values are seen in UK DSGE literature (Harrison and Oomen, 2010; Chen and McDonald, 2011; Faccini, Millard and Zanetti, 2011). Inertial lags used in existing literature but not this model do not significantly affect the results but instead do not smooth the monetary authority's reaction to the shock.

The value of ϵ , the share of workers with health shock sensitivity, is set to 0.45, as justified by section 4.1. To understand the appropriate calibration value of the elasticity of substitution between workers, ν , first consider that UK employers face anti-discrimination laws such as the Equality Act 2010 and must make reasonable accommodations (e.g., health assessments) to prevent dismissal under bouts of absenteeism or presenteeism. This point suggests that type-S and N workers have a low degree of substitution. A worker can neither choose to be sensitive to health shocks in the short run. However, León-Ledesma, McAdam and Wilman (2011) observe workers with skill differentials have found elasticities of substitution of higher than 1, which must also have some influence in the calibration if sick workers have, on average, lower productivities and less time to learn skills. Furthermore, Jäger and Heining (2022) use data to find workers' wages benefit from their co-workers' deaths; this is likely true on a smaller scale for absenteeism, perhaps reflecting picking up their work by working overtime hours at a higher wage. Matsui and Yoshimi (2015) set ν equal to -10 in their baseline and 0.6 in their alternative scenario. In this case, ν is set to -0.25 such that the elasticity of substitution is 0.8, so type-S and N workers are weak complements. The results are sensitive to this elasticity's calibration value as it reflects the efficiency at which resources are reallocated to each labour type after a shock.

The baseline aggregate productivity shock's persistence, ρ_A , is set to 0.95, which shows that the size of the shock will diminish by 5% in each period. As the nature of presenteeism is

long-term, the persistence of this shock, ρ_2 , is also set to 0.95, which aids in comparability with the baseline. This parameter suggests that a presenteeism-like health shock has a half-life of about thirteen periods (around four years if quarters). Finally, the absenteeism shock persistence parameter, ρ_1 , is set to 0.05, suggesting the IRFs will show a significant impact within the first period and then a small residual because workers recover from illness quickly.

Table 1: Calibration values.

Symbol	Name	Value	Source
β	Time Discounting Factor	0.99	Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011)
σ	Relative Risk Aversion Coefficient	0.66	Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011)
γ	Frisch Labour Supply Elasticity	1	Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011)
ω	Degree of Calvo Price Stickiness	0.7	Dixon and Tian (2017)
ϕ_π	Inflation Parameter in Taylor Rule	1.5	Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011)
ϕ_Y	Output Gap Parameter in Taylor Rule	0.25	Faccini, Millard and Zanetti (2011)
ϵ	Weight of Health-Sensitive Workers	0.45	DWP (2014), Vitality (2020)
ν	CES Labour Elasticity of Substitution	-0.25	Author calibration
ρ_A	Persistence of Productivity Shock	0.95	Author calibration
ρ_1	Persistence of Absenteeism Shock	0.05	Author calibration
ρ_2	Persistence of Presenteeism Shock	0.95	Author calibration

The four steady states of endogenous variables (Table 2) represent values they would attain if there were no shocks and provide a benchmark for analysing deviations from long-run equilibrium. Uhlig's (1999) method was applied to log-linearise the system of equations around the steady-state values, summarised in Appendix 8.3. Endogenous variables in terms of log deviations around a steady state are denoted with a hat.

For the steady-state values, prices, P , and the labour force, L , are normalised to 1, given that there are no other inputs in the production function, whereby $L_U + L_N = 1$, following Matsui and Yoshimi (2015). Steady-state values for type-S and N workers reflect the parameter ϵ .

Table 2: Steady-state values.

Symbol	Name	Value	Source
P	Price Level	1	Matsui and Yoshimi (2015)
L	Labour Force	1	Author calibration
L_S	Health Sensitive Labour Force	0.45	DWP (2014), Vitality (2020)
L_N	Health Insensitive Labour Force	0.55	DWP (2014), Vitality (2020)

5 Results

5.1 Impulse Response Functions

5.1.1 Baseline Aggregate Productivity Shock

Productivity gains have occurred in the UK since the financial crisis in some regard. For example, technological progress has allowed firms to make more efficient use of labour in productivity (i.e., Figure 1 shows a shallow positive trend). The baseline scenario in Figure 4 shows a small positive aggregate productivity shock (1%), which materialises via the parameter A_t . The shock reduces firm marginal costs and causes disinflation and a fall in the nominal interest rate as households anticipate a persistent decline in inflation under rational expectations; this causes consumption and output to increase in the current and future periods. The baseline characterises the economic state with zero health shocks, and all workers are healthy. Adverse health shocks mute the benefits of aggregate productivity shocks, and endogenizing health using type-S and N workers will illustrate this effect.

Figure 4: Baseline scenario – 1% positive aggregate productivity shock.

The IRFs show the most impact within the first of the 40 periods. As expected, the aggregate productivity shock suggests a positive 1% deviation from the steady state in output and

consumption. Aggregate real wages and labour supply also increased against their steady states by 0.8% and 0.06%, respectively. The shock has a homogenous effect on type-S and N workers, both reaping the wage and employment benefits of new technology equally. The real marginal cost fell 0.2% below its steady state as firms benefitted from productivity gains. Finally, the shock has a small disinflationary effect (0.6% below steady state), which prompts the monetary authority to lower nominal interest rates by a similar amount.

5.1.2 Absenteeism Shock

This model simulates an asymmetric work absence shock to type-S workers via the parameter $\chi_{1,t}$. The shock occurs every period because a share of the labour force suffers from mild sickness each quarter. Some residual effect from the shock is seen in subsequent periods due to non-zero shock persistence. The IRFs are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Absenteeism scenario – negative 1% work absence shock.

The shock is sharp and significant and affects all endogenous variables, but workers recover quickly, given that they are rehabilitating at home rather than working. Work absence means firms produce fewer output units; thus, output and consumption fall by 0.07%. However, there are asymmetric effects between type-S and N workers. Type-S workers are most harshly

affected; this causes a 0.3% decrease in their productive hours as they are off work; meanwhile, type-N labour increases by 0.1% to pick up the slack of sick workers. Interestingly, this is not a one-to-one offset due to the asymmetric changes in aggregate real wages and workers' elasticity of substitution; the reduction in type-S labour caused type-S real wages to rise 0.6% above the steady state as workers willing to work on S-contracts become scarcer. Aggregate wages rose by 0.3%, and type-N real wages grew by 0.08%. Lastly, the absence shock is inflationary, increasing by 0.05% above the steady state.

A combined shock impulse is found to assess the absence shock versus the baseline by summing the IRFs as the model is linear (Figure 6). Given its persistence, the effect on output is small relative to the aggregate productivity shock. However, as the shock is frequent, its effects have likely accumulated over time on the productive capacity of the UK economy. The reduction in the labour supply of type-S workers is about five times larger than the positive effect in the baseline scenario. Meanwhile, the positive impact on type-N labour supply is approximately three times as large. This result emphasises the extremity of absence shocks on each type of labour supply. This is due to the hypersensitivity of the elasticity of substitution, ν , showing firms substitute type-S workers for type-N workers. Yet, the effect of the absence shock on aggregate labour supply neutralises that of the aggregate productivity shock due to the offsetting impacts between the two types of workers.

ONS (2023a) and Vitality (2024) show that absent days per worker are 5.7 in 2022 and 6.1 in 2023, respectively. Assuming 260 working days per annum and adjusting for the number of those known not to take absence using the model's calibration parameters, this approximates a negative 5% reduction in productive hours of type-S workers. This magnitude is consistent with approximately a 16% productivity shock and equates to around 1.2% of output loss, amounting to £28 billion, a similar magnitude to the £17 billion estimate implied by Vitality (2024). A 16% productivity shock is immense; however, the baseline has zero absence. In context of the productivity puzzle, the ONS (2023a) reported that the average absent days per worker in the 2010s was 4.4, indicating an increase of ~1.5 days since, consistent with a smaller 4% decline in productivity. Testing the results' reliability is difficult, as no counterfactual or macroeconomic data disaggregates the outcomes of type-S and N workers.

Figure 6: Absenteeism and baseline scenarios. The black line shows the baseline scenario, while the dashed blue line shows the work absence and baseline shocks combined.

5.1.3 Presenteeism Shock

The presenteeism shock is assumed to show the same level of persistence as the baseline. Figure 7 reproduces a negative 1% asymmetric shock on the production function parameter $\chi_{2,t}$. This shock is over five times more harmful to output and consumption than the work absence shock, contracting by 0.4% from its steady state. Furthermore, there is a decrease in type-S and N labour supply by 0.2% and 0.06%, respectively, lower than the effects of the absenteeism shock as type-S labour is still in work but is not working as efficiently. There is also a heterogeneous effect on type-S workers' real wages, which decreases by 0.4%. Meanwhile, type-N workers' real wage decreases by 0.3%. Crucially, this outcome shows that if an individual decides to continue working when ill, it will affect all those in work and make them less productive, even if not sensitive directly to health shocks representing a negative externality. Practically, this could reflect decreased benefits of economies of scale or diseconomies of scale (e.g., poor communication), delays in work deliverables and the effect on firm culture – these factors weigh on output. The real wage index increases by 0.9% even when all workers' real wages are declining because this is where $\chi_{2,t}$ appears in the log-

linearised system. The shock has a more considerable inflationary impact, adding 0.2% versus the steady state level, over three times greater than the absenteeism scenario. Finally, the representative firm's real marginal cost increases by 0.09%.

Figure 7: Presenteeism scenario – negative 1% productivity shock to those in work.

Figure 8 illustrates that the presenteeism shock removes around 40% of the gains in growth and consumption from the baseline. It also reduces the wage increases for type-S and type-N workers by 55% and 40%, respectively. Furthermore, it overcompensates the increase in aggregate labour hours, type-S workers suffer a 0.1% decline overall, while type-N workers' hours are roughly constant. The benefit to marginal cost declines by around 40% due to the negative health shock; if only the UK experiences such shock, this may reduce international competitiveness. Relative to the baseline, the monetary authority responds differently, only reducing nominal interest rates by 0.4%. A drawback of the model could be considered from how the presenteeism shock is modelled as temporary, when in fact the worker may make themselves more ill by attending work (i.e., a permanent shock), but this reinforces the conclusion that presenteeism's severity is more concerning than absenteeism.

As discussed in section 4.1, Vitality (2024) states that 43.6 days per worker on average were lost due to presenteeism in 2023, equivalent to 16.7% of the total working hours of all workers. The model cannot simulate such a significant productivity shock that will affect the hours worked by this magnitude. However, Vitality (2024) implied an output loss of £121 billion (5.3% of GDP) from presenteeism; the productivity shock size consistent with this output loss is around 14% against a baseline with no long-term ill health. As a proxy, the amount of economically active individuals due to long-term sickness has increased by 30% since the 2010s average, implying only a 4% productivity shock, comparable to the realistic absenteeism shock's size. A drawback of the model is the simplicity of the production function which is unable to show a change in output per labour hours worked (as without an aggregate productivity shock, $A_t = 1$ and $Y_t = L_t$). Ideally, this would show that the decline in hours worked is less than the decline in output over time.

Figure 8: Presenteeism and baseline scenarios. The black line shows the baseline scenario, while the dashed red line shows the productivity loss in work and baseline shocks combined.

Overall, the results show that a work absence shock delivers a harsh immediate impact on economic outcomes, yet this period helps workers recover away from work. As the persistence of the shock is small, they can quickly return to near-maximum productivity in

the subsequent periods. Meanwhile, presenteeism shows that during a period of physical or mental illness, the instantaneous shock on labour supply is less significant. However, its persistence and negative externalities on co-workers make the period intrinsically worse than simply staying home and recovering. It takes a long time to recover from long-term illnesses, yet this is where business strategies and fiscal policy have significantly more influence and can embed measures to help workers, particularly the young, to take control of their health.

5.2 Discussion

To evaluate the UK Government and firms' policies minimising absenteeism and presenteeism, consider workers' incentives when ill (adaptation to a health shock) and when not ill (mitigation of health shocks). For governments, absenteeism-related policies consist of sick pay, which prevents individual health shocks from turning into family-sized shocks, and services to help advise workers to recover quickly (e.g., GPs and NHS 111). For presenteeism longer-term policies are required, such as building NHS capacity, medical innovations, and information campaigns. For corporates, this involves embedding strategies to add additional benefits to remove the stigma around taking sick days, aligning with health and safety regulation and arrangements for workers whose long-term illness is preventing them from working at maximum capacity. If a firm has a workforce with a high average tenure, it has greater control over incentives to maintain workers' long-term health and presenteeism rates.

UK statutory sick pay (SSP) is argued to incentivise presenteeism. The effect on marginal cost within the first period is three times higher for absenteeism than presenteeism, yet presenteeism lasts for several periods, so a non-myopic growth-promoting government strictly prefers workers to be ill and recover quickly. As the model observes, sick pay also forces a negative externality on other health-insensitive workers' wages and reduces their productive hours worked. UK SSP is £116.75 per week, paid by the employer (around 1/6th of the average weekly wage) for up to 28 weeks (GOV.UK, 2024). Its coverage is also low; workers must be on an employment contract, have done at least four weeks of work, have been sick for four or more days, and earn an average of at least £120 per week. The size of SSP is criticised for being ungenerous compared to the OECD average of 60% pre-pandemic. Also, two million workers cannot access SSP (Brewer and Gustafsson, 2020). Those who place the highest social value on sick pay are least likely to have access (Adams-Prassl et al., 2023); this means that workers who should be taking work absences are forced to work as they cannot afford to lose wages and consequently are less productive. Furthermore, Bryson

and Dale-Olsen (2017) find that absenteeism rates are more sensitive to sick pay in countries with higher rates, so small SSP changes may disproportionately reduce presenteeism risk. On the contrary, a 2010 study showed that 93.1% of large corporates had a supplementary sickness policy (XpertHR, 2010), such as full pay for a short period which often increased the with tenure, so the international comparisons at the state level may be unfair. Nonetheless, a reform of SSP could aid workers in taking sickness absence and prevent presenteeism.

Firms also implement other pay incentive structures that prevent high absenteeism rates and encourage presenteeism. There is evidence that working too hard contributes to poor health. For example, Green and Heywood (2023) find that performance pay schemes are associated with more hours worked and a higher probability of working very long hours. Yet, the authors find that after controlling for sorting (workers who prefer to work longer hours sort into payment by performance), the effects from longer hours appear too small to explain all negative health effects. Instead, the decline in health observed may be through trauma and externalities in social and family life rather than the direct effect of working long hours. Secondly, work-from-home policies that materialised from the pandemic have meant that workers feel like they can work with less effort (i.e., do not have to travel to work), which further risks presenteeism; Martin (2023) suggests that management provision and workplace culture regimes regarding worker health should be encouraged, particularly after the pandemic in which over 2.9 million people have had long-COVID. The notion of being ‘too scared to go sick’ is not new; Taylor et al. (2010) initially highlighted that when job security is concerned individuals tend to attend work when ill, and this was further brought to light during the pandemic (Hadjisolomou, 2016; Hadjisolomou, Mitsakis and Gary, 2022). This evidence illustrates that firms have some control over their internal rates of absenteeism and presenteeism; it is in firms’ best interest to reconsider these schemes as they reduce productive work hours. Restructuring these schemes across large employers may lower marginal costs and thus increase the UK’s international competitiveness and productivity.

Strained national health services reduce the efficiency of government funds to alleviate presenteeism. Poor national health policies increase the share of people vulnerable to health shocks, including those working in the healthcare sector. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused an exponential increase in healthcare treatment backlogs; in 2023, there were 7.5 million waiting for treatments, with 40% waiting longer than 18 weeks (NHS England, 2024a). Pressure to reduce backlogs has caused absenteeism and presenteeism in the

healthcare sector. Marciniak-Nuqui, Cabling and Romanelli (2024) interviewed primary and secondary care workers who stated that sickness absence is forcing healthcare workers to operate without full staff capacity, reducing the quality of care. Furthermore, workers' indispensability and the NHS' ethos of determination have induced a culture of normalised presenteeism. The UK Government has attempted to increase graduate medical placements but lacks a retention plan to reduce the high levels of vacancies (Khan, 2023). A shortage of medical staff will be less able to supply productive hours to clear the high demand for healthcare services. Continued presenteeism will weigh on healthcare and aggregate output, reducing the UK's dynamism to respond to other financial and geopolitical shocks.

The UK Government's Back to Work Plan (GOV.UK, 2023) aims to aid 1.1 million people with long-term health conditions back to work. In 2023, around 30% of those who were economically inactive reasoned that they were temporarily or long-term ill (ONS, 2023f), concentrated in the age range of 50-64 years. The plan includes reforming fit note processes, mental health counselling, individual placement, and support (IPS) schemes, as well as preventing vulnerable groups from falling into long-term unemployment. These measures focus on individuals with common chronic and mental illnesses causing presenteeism, and it may be a cost-effective method to bring people back into work. However, except for synergies of new skill combinations from workers re-entering the labour force, the policy does not directly target productivity shortfalls by increasing output per worker. While making logistical arrangements to get the economically inactive back into work will improve absolute output, it fails to address their illness. Under the terms of the model, this policy will increase the share of health-sensitive workers in the labour force and the levels of overall presenteeism and absenteeism under a health shock. Besides boosting labour participation through these arrangements, policies that rely on the long-term sick to resolve current labour market shortages may not be economical. Instead, encouraging health-insensitive foreign workers to migrate to the UK will reduce the impact of negative health shocks.

Finally, the ONS reports productivity without specific regard to presenteeism, as there is no adjustment to whether the hours are productive, like in the model. Unadjusted hours worked are greater than productive hours worked, which deflates the level of labour productivity reported. Thus, poor worker health is likely one aspect of the UK productivity puzzle and may also be the case across developed countries experiencing similar TFP stagnations.

6 Conclusion

In this dissertation, the NK DSGE model endogenized health-sensitive and insensitive workers and simulated negative health shocks against a positive productivity shock. Health shocks adversely impact the productivity shock's benefits, and thus can likely explain part of the UK's TFP stagnation and productivity puzzle, a conclusion which may be used in future international literature. A 1% presenteeism shock has a 0.4% immediate effect on economic output, around five times larger than an equivalent absenteeism shock. Importantly, a presenteeism shock imposes negative externalities on health-insensitive workers' wages and productive labour supply. To minimise the impact of presenteeism, individuals must be advised to undergo restitution and recover from their illness before attending work. Higher rates of absenteeism in the short run will allow for lower rates of presenteeism in the long run and benefit structural labour productivity. Individuals control their health sensitivity, an inference that aligns with existing health economics literature, so their actions are influenced by policies that aim to reduce the share of health-sensitive individuals in the workforce.

To achieve this, governments could readdress the breadth of SSP and increase digitalisation to alleviate some monotonous tasks from health service workers, reducing the impact on their health and their presenteeism risk. Additional public investment, along with a healthcare retention plan, could be utilised to alleviate staff shortages and improve the quality of care (e.g., by accessing new medical technology, equipment, and medicines). Secondly, because the model found that firms have incentives to lower internal presenteeism and absenteeism rates given its impact on their marginal costs, the private sector could also implement strategies to encourage restitution and provide workers access to benefits such as fitness classes and health check-ups to minimise presenteeism. Access to new technology will decrease disutility of work and improve workplace cultures. These policies will reduce the share of health-sensitive workers, alleviating output loss, lower employment, stagnant real wages and inflationary pressure upon a health shock and thus increase the UK's dynamism.

Long-term sickness has reduced labour force participation, but its effect on aggregate productivity is likely small. This simplification provides an opportunity for future research to augment the model and observe the effects of ill health on the economically inactive, search frictions, and job-matching efficiency. However, future academic work is dependent upon the ability of governments and research institutions to publish sufficient data on absenteeism and

presenteeism, which has been the primary factor as to why health has been overlooked in the labour productivity debate. Furthermore, research must consider the interdependence between health-sensitive and health-insensitive workers. Overall, more complete information on the health of the workforce will allow the discovery of the extent to which health shocks have harmed the UK and ultimately global economic outcomes.

7 Bibliography

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8 Appendix

8.1 Household Optimisation

8.1.1 Derivation of Household Expenditure Minimisation

Households minimise total expenditure on all differentiated consumption goods, c_j , for any level of the composite consumption good, C_t :

$$\min_{c_{jt}} \int_0^1 p_{jt} c_{jt} dj \quad (8.1)$$

Subject to:

$$C_t = \left[\int_0^1 c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{\theta-1}} \quad (8.2)$$

The optimisation problem is defined as below, where the Lagrange multiplier is ψ_t :

$$L = \int_0^1 p_{jt} c_{jt} dj - \psi_t \left\{ \left[\int_0^1 c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{\theta-1}} - C_t \right\}, \theta > 1 \quad (8.3)$$

The first-order condition is described as:

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta c_{jt}} = p_{jt} - \psi_t \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \left[\int_0^1 c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{\theta-1}-1} \frac{\theta-1}{\theta} c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}-1} = 0 \quad (8.4)$$

$$p_{jt} = \psi_t \left[\int_0^1 c_{jt}^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{1}{\theta-1}} c_{jt}^{\frac{1}{\theta}} = \psi_t C_t^{\frac{1}{\theta}} c_{jt}^{\frac{1}{\theta}} \quad (8.5)$$

Rearrange the first-order condition:

$$c_{jt} = \left(\frac{p_{jt}}{\psi_t} \right)^{-\theta} C_t \quad (8.6)$$

To find the value of the Lagrange multiplier, insert the result in equation 8.6 into the first-order condition. The value of the Lagrange multiplier is identical to the aggregate price level.

$$C_t = \left[\int_0^1 \left(\frac{p_{jt}}{\psi_t} \right)^{-\theta} C_t^{\frac{\theta-1}{\theta}} dj \right]^{\frac{\theta}{\theta-1}} \quad (8.7)$$

$$\psi_t = \left[\int_0^1 p_{jt}^{1-\theta} dj \right]^{\frac{1}{1-\theta}} \equiv P_t \quad (8.8)$$

Substituting equation 8.8 into equation 8.6 specifies the demand index:

$$c_{jt} = \left(\frac{p_{jt}}{P_t} \right)^{-\theta} C_t \quad (8.9)$$

8.1.2 Derivation of Household Optimisation

The representative household maximises its expected lifetime utility:

$$\max_{C_t, B_t, L_{S,t}, L_{N,t}} E_t \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \beta^t \left[\frac{C_t^{1-\sigma}}{1-\sigma} - \frac{L_{S,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} - \frac{L_{N,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} \right] \right\} \quad (8.10)$$

Subject to its budget constraint:

$$P_t C_t + Q_t B_t \leq B_{t-1} + w_{S,t} \chi_{1,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} + \Pi_t \quad (8.11)$$

The Lagrangean and first order conditions are described below, λ_t^h is the Lagrange multiplier:

$$L = E_t \left\{ \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \beta^t \left[\frac{C_t^{1-\sigma}}{1-\sigma} - \frac{L_{S,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} - \frac{L_{N,t}^{1+\gamma}}{1+\gamma} \right] \right\} + \lambda_t^h [B_{t-1} + w_{S,t} \chi_{1,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} + \Pi_t - P_t C_t - Q_t B_t] \quad (8.12)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta C_t} = C_t^{-\sigma} - \lambda_t^h P_t = 0 \quad (8.13)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta B_t} = \beta E_t \lambda_{t+1}^h - \lambda_t^h Q_t = 0 \quad (8.14)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta L_{S,t}} = -L_{S,t}^\gamma + \lambda_t^h w_{S,t} \chi_{1,t} = 0 \quad (8.15)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta L_{N,t}} = -L_{N,t}^\gamma + \lambda_t^h w_{N,t} = 0 \quad (8.16)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta \lambda_t^h} = B_{t-1} + w_{S,t} \chi_{1,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} + \Pi_t - P_t C_t - Q_t B_t = 0 \quad (8.17)$$

The Euler equation is derived by substituting equation 8.13 into 8.14 to cancel out λ_t^h .

$$\beta E_t \left(\frac{C_{t+1}^{-\sigma}}{P_{t+1}} \right) = \left(\frac{C_t^{-\sigma}}{P_t} \right) Q_t \quad (8.18)$$

Using the approximation $r_t \approx -\ln(Q_t)$ and the definition for the change in the price level:

$$C_t^{-\sigma} = \beta(1 + r_t) E_t \left(\frac{C_{t+1}^{-\sigma}}{1 + \pi_{t+1}} \right) \quad (8.19)$$

The labour-leisure trade-off is derived by substituting equation 8.13 into 8.15 and 8.16 to cancel out λ_t^h .

$$\frac{\chi_{1,t} w_{S,t}}{P_t} = L_{S,t}^\gamma C_t^\sigma \quad (8.20)$$

$$\frac{w_{N,t}}{P_t} = L_{N,t}^\gamma C_t^\sigma \quad (8.21)$$

8.2 Firm Optimisation

8.2.1 Derivation of Cost Minimisation

The firm minimises its labour costs with respect to each type of labour:

$$\min_{L_{S,t}, L_{N,t}} w_{S,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} \quad (8.22)$$

Subject to the aggregate labour index:

$$L_t = \left\{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \right\}^{\frac{1}{\nu}} \quad (8.23)$$

These equations form the optimisation problem below, λ_t^f is the Lagrange multiplier:

$$L = w_{S,t} L_{S,t} + w_{N,t} L_{N,t} + \lambda_t^f \left(L_t - \left\{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \right\}^{\frac{1}{\nu}} \right) \quad (8.24)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta L_{S,t}} = w_{S,t} - \lambda_t^f \left(\epsilon \chi_{2,t}^\nu L_{S,t}^{\nu-1} \left\{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \right\}^{\frac{1-\nu}{\nu}} \right) = 0 \quad (8.25)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta L_{N,t}} = w_{N,t} - \lambda_t^f \left((1 - \epsilon) L_{N,t}^{\nu-1} \{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \}^{\frac{1-\nu}{\nu}} \right) = 0 \quad (8.26)$$

$$\frac{\delta L}{\delta \lambda_t^f} = L_t - \{ \epsilon [\chi_{2,t} L_{S,t}]^\nu + (1 - \epsilon) [L_{N,t}]^\nu \}^{\frac{1}{\nu}} = 0 \quad (8.27)$$

Rearranging equations 8.25 and 8.26 and substituting into equation 8.27 derives:

$$\left[\frac{w_{S,t}}{\chi_{2,t} \epsilon \lambda_t^f L_t^{1-\nu}} \right]^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} = \chi_{2,t} L_{S,t} \quad (8.28)$$

$$\left[\frac{w_{N,t}}{(1 - \epsilon) \lambda_t^f L_t^{1-\nu}} \right]^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} = L_{N,t} \quad (8.29)$$

$$L_t = \left\{ \epsilon \left[\frac{w_{S,t}}{\chi_{2,t} \lambda_t^f L_t^{1-\nu}} \right]^{\frac{\nu}{\nu-1}} + (1 - \epsilon) \left[\frac{w_{N,t}}{(1 - \epsilon) \lambda_t^f L_t^{1-\nu}} \right]^{\frac{\nu}{\nu-1}} \right\}^{\frac{1}{\nu}} \quad (8.30)$$

Thus, the Lagrange multiplier can be written as the wage index:

$$\lambda_t^f = w_t = \left\{ \epsilon^{\frac{1}{1-\nu}} \left[\frac{w_{S,t}}{\chi_{2,t}} \right]^{\frac{\nu}{\nu-1}} + (1 - \epsilon)^{\frac{1}{1-\nu}} [w_{N,t}]^{\frac{\nu}{\nu-1}} \right\}^{\frac{\nu-1}{\nu}} \quad (8.31)$$

Equation 8.31 is then used to derive the firm labour demands:

$$L_{S,t} = \chi_{2,t}^{\frac{\nu}{1-\nu}} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon} \frac{w_{S,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} L_t \quad (8.32)$$

$$L_{N,t} = \left(\frac{1}{1 - \epsilon} \frac{w_{N,t}}{w_t} \right)^{\frac{1}{\nu-1}} L_t \quad (8.33)$$

8.2.2 Derivation of Optimal Price Setting

The representative firm sets an optimal price, p_{jt}^* , to maximise the expected value of discounted future profits, total revenues, $p_{jt}^* y_{jt+k,t}$, minus total costs, $t c_{jt,t+k}$, which are function of output, while the price remains effective:

$$\max_{p_{jt}^*} E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} [p_{jt}^* y_{jt+k,t} - t c_{jt+k,t}(y_{jt+k,t})] \right\} \quad (8.34)$$

Subject to:

$$y_{jt+k,t} = \left(\frac{p_{jt}^*}{P_{t+k}} \right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} \quad (8.35)$$

The term $y_{jt+k,t}$ represents the output of a representative firm in period $t+k$ that last set its price in period t . The discount rate is defined as:

$$\Delta_{t,t+k} = \frac{1}{1+r_t} = \beta^k \left(\frac{C_{t+k}}{C_t} \right)^{-\sigma} E_t \left(\frac{P_t}{P_{t+k}} \right) \quad (8.36)$$

Substituting the constraint into the maximisation problem:

$$\max_{p_{jt}^*} E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} \left[p_{jt}^* \left(\frac{p_{jt}^*}{P_{t+k}} \right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} - t c_{jt+k,t} \left(\left(\frac{p_{jt}^*}{P_{t+k}} \right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} \right) \right] \right\} \quad (8.37)$$

Finding the first order condition:

$$\frac{\delta}{\delta p_{jt}^*} = E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} y_{jt+k,t} \left[(1-\theta) + \theta m c_{jt+k,t} \left(\frac{1}{p_{jt}^*} \right) \right] \right\} = 0 \quad (8.38)$$

As all firms prefer to set the same optimal price, the j subscript can be dropped, $p_{jt}^* = p_t^*$.

Rewrite equation 8.38 by multiplying the terms inside the brackets by $\frac{p_t^*}{(1-\theta)}$:

$$E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} y_{t+k,t} \left[p_t^* - \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} m c_{t+k,t} \right] \right\} = 0 \quad (8.39)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} y_{t+k,t} p_t^* = \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega^k \Delta_{t,t+k} y_{t+k,t} m c_{t+k,t} \quad (8.40)$$

Substituting the definitions of $y_{t+k,t}$ and $\Delta_{t,t+k}$ into the expression and solving for p_t^* :

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k \left(\frac{C_{t+k}}{C_t}\right)^{-\sigma} \frac{P_t}{P_{t+k}} \left(\frac{p_t^*}{P_{t+k}}\right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} p_t^* \\ &= \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k \left(\frac{C_{t+k}}{C_t}\right)^{-\sigma} \frac{P_t}{P_{t+k}} \left(\frac{p_t^*}{P_{t+k}}\right)^{-\theta} C_{t+k} m c_{t+k,t} \end{aligned} \quad (8.41)$$

$$p_t^* = \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \frac{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} P_{t+k}^{\theta-1} m c_{t+k,t} \right\}}{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} P_{t+k}^{\theta-1} \right\}} \quad (8.42)$$

Further divide by P_t to derive the optimal real price:

$$\frac{p_t^*}{P_t} = \frac{\theta}{\theta-1} \frac{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} \left(\frac{P_{t+k}}{P_t}\right)^{\theta-1} \left(\frac{m c_{t+k,t}}{P_t}\right) \right\}}{E_t \left\{ \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (\omega\beta)^k C_{t+k}^{1-\sigma} \left(\frac{P_{t+k}}{P_t}\right)^{\theta-1} \right\}} \quad (8.43)$$

8.3 System of Log-linearised Equations

There are 12 endogenous variables and 3 exogenous shock variables. The steady state values for $w_{S,t}$, $w_{N,t}$ and w_t are W_S , W_N and W respectively. The log-linearised system is built with the equations specified below.

Euler equation:

$$\sigma(\hat{C}_{t+1} - \hat{C}_t) = \hat{r}_t - E_t \pi_{t+1} \quad (8.44)$$

Production function:

$$\hat{Y}_t = \hat{A}_t + \hat{L}_t \quad (8.45)$$

Labour demand for type-S and type-N workers:

$$\hat{L}_{S,t} = \frac{1}{\nu-1} (\hat{w}_{S,t} - \hat{w}_t - \nu \hat{\chi}_{2,t}) + \hat{L}_t \quad (8.46)$$

$$\hat{L}_{N,t} = \frac{1}{\nu-1} (\hat{w}_{N,t} - \hat{w}_t) + \hat{L}_t \quad (8.47)$$

Labour supply for type-S and type-N workers:

$$\hat{w}_{S,t} - \hat{P}_t = \gamma \hat{L}_{S,t} + \sigma \hat{C}_t - \hat{\chi}_{1,t} \quad (8.48)$$

$$\widehat{w}_{N,t} - \widehat{P}_t = \gamma \widehat{L}_{N,t} + \sigma \widehat{C}_t \quad (8.49)$$

Aggregate wage index:

$$\widehat{w}_t = \epsilon^{\frac{1}{1-\nu}} \left(\frac{W_S}{W} \right)^{\frac{\nu}{\nu-1}} (\widehat{w}_{S,t} - \widehat{\chi}_{2,t}) + (1 - \epsilon)^{\frac{1}{1-\nu}} \left(\frac{W_N}{W} \right) (\widehat{w}_{N,t}) \quad (8.50)$$

Nominal marginal cost:

$$\widehat{m}c_t = \widehat{w}_t - \widehat{A}_t \quad (8.51)$$

NK Phillips Curve:

$$\pi_t = \beta E_t \pi_{t+1} + \frac{(1 - \omega)(1 - \beta\omega)}{\omega} (\widehat{m}c_t - \widehat{P}_t) \quad (8.52)$$

Goods market equilibrium:

$$\widehat{Y}_t = \widehat{C}_t \quad (8.53)$$

Inflation rate:

$$\pi_t = \widehat{P}_t - \widehat{P}_{t-1} \quad (8.54)$$

Monetary policy Taylor rule:

$$\widehat{r}_t = \phi_\pi \pi_t + \phi_Y \widehat{Y}_t + e_r \quad (8.55)$$

Exogeneous shocks:

$$\widehat{A}_t = \rho_A \widehat{A}_{t-1} + e_{A,t} \quad (8.56)$$

$$\widehat{\chi}_{1,t} = \rho_1 \widehat{\chi}_{1,t-1} + e_{1,t} \quad (8.57)$$

$$\widehat{\chi}_{2,t} = \rho_2 \widehat{\chi}_{2,t-1} + e_{2,t} \quad (8.58)$$